

Research Article

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Subtle bias, lasting impact: Gendered microaggressions in Ghana's higher education institutions

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Abstract: This paper investigates the everyday enactment of gendered microaggressions and benevolent sexism in Ghanaian universities, highlighting their role as informal mechanisms that sustain gendered hierarchies despite formal commitments to equality. Drawing on feminist theoretical frameworks and qualitative methodologies, the study is based on semi-structured, in-depth interviews with female faculty members and doctoral candidates across multiple Ghanaian higher education institutions. Analysis illustrates how discrete interpersonal experiences and gender-coded deferential terminology, such as referring to female faculty as "Mummy" or "Auntie" express immersive assumptions about femininity, care work, and emotional labour which, often justified as expressions of cultural respect, subtly erode women's professional authority and normalize unequal treatment. Exploration of these discourses demonstrate how narratives of meritocracy and gender equality obscure structural inequalities by displacing responsibility onto individuals or cultural norms rather than

institutional arrangements. Participants' narratives highlight both the durability of institutionalized sexism, and the diverse strategies women deploy to navigate, contest, and reconfigure these dynamics, including pedagogies of discomfort and dialogic, collaborative modes of engagement. The paper contends that addressing gender inequality in Ghanaian higher education requires moving beyond formal policy frameworks to critically examine the micro-level practices through which power is enacted and sustained.

Keywords – Academic culture, Gender microaggressions, Ghana, Nego-feminism, Professional development, Sociology

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender research and advocacy centres within Ghanaian universities emerged in response to persistent inequities embedded within both formal and informal institutional structures. These centres have formalized the once-invisible gendered dynamics of the university, asserted women's intellectual legitimacy and created avenues for advocacy, research, and the adjudication of gender-based discrimination and harassment. Their establishment reflects a growing recognition that gendered experiences in higher education cannot be fully understood or addressed through policy reforms alone, but must also contend with the "unwritten codes and conventions" that shape behaviour, discourse, and opportunity (Britwum et al., 2014: 5). Yet, despite their existence and the progress they symbolize, subtle and pervasive mechanisms of inequality continue to reproduce gender hierarchies within academic spaces.

Situated within a broader study investigating how higher education is perceived, navigated, and experienced by women academics in Ghana, and addressing the research question of how achievement and status are defined, negotiated, and shaped by social actors, this article examines how benevolent sexism and microaggressions operate within Ghanaian university settings as informal mechanisms that sustain patriarchal power relations. Drawing from participants' experiences and critical feminist theory, it interrogates how everyday interactions such as addressing female faculty as "Mummy" or "Auntie" reinforce gendered assumptions of care and emotional labour, while sustaining deference along gendered lines. Although these practices can seem innocuous or be interpreted as respectful, they diminish professional authority and reinforce essentialist notions of women's roles within academic and social hierarchies.

Through the narratives of women faculty who navigate, challenge, and reframe these gendered expectations, this paper explores how informal discourses of benevolent sexism and microaggressions function both as barriers and sites of resistance. In doing so, it illuminates the dual processes by which women in academia are simultaneously marginalized and empowered (Sall, 2000), confronting discrimination through critical engagement, pedagogies of discomfort, and nego-feminist practices (Nnaemeka, 2003) that emphasize collaboration, reflection, and shared responsibility. Ultimately, the article argues that recognizing and addressing these subtle, systemic forms of discrimination is essential to advancing genuine gender equity in Ghanaian higher education and transforming the ideological and institutional foundations that sustain inequality.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OR METHODS

The study is anchored in feminist and nego-feminist theoretical frameworks that conceptualize sexism as both structural and relational. Drawing on the works of Nnaemeka (2003), Manuh (2007), Manne (2018) and Kiprop (2025) situates microaggressions and benevolent sexism within broader patriarchal and fraternal systems that regulate women's participation in higher education. Benevolent sexism (Becker & Swim, 2011) is used to show how seemingly respectful or caring behaviours reinforce women's subordination by naturalizing gendered caregiving roles and microaggression theory (Basford et al., 2014; Sue et al., 2008) provides the analytical lens to understand how subtle acts sustain institutional inequality. Nego-feminism (Nnaemeka, 2003) informs the study's praxis-oriented focus, emphasizing negotiation, collaboration, and the creation of reflective solidarity through critical dialogue. Together, these frameworks illuminate how informal, cultural practices perpetuate gendered power relations even within ostensibly egalitarian institutional spaces, while also offering pathways for transformative resistance.

This study employed qualitative, interpretive methods to explore the perspectives and experiences of women academics in Ghanaian universities. Participants were recruited through participant referrals and targeted requests from a variety of faculties including liberal arts, professional studies, social sciences and sciences, totalling 23 interviews with women academics in positions ranging from PhD candidate to Dean across four universities, two of which are included in this article. This selection of participants allows for comparative analysis and insights on the impacts of gender dynamics on career progression and institutional contexts. With participants consent, conversations were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. Coding and interpretation process was guided by thematic analysis, with particular attention paid to recurring patterns, convergences and divergences within and between participants' narratives.

Talk data was collected through one-on-one, in-depth, open-ended, semi-structured interviews. Interviews were conducted in person and ranged from one to two hours, utilizing an interview guide that highlighted key areas of research, maintaining continuity between interview participants. In recognition that knowledge and interviews are "created together" (Greenspan & Bolkosky, 2006: 432), the open-ended structure allowed the interviews to also be guided by participants. "Open" questions created space for fluid conversations and adaptation to personal

experiences and interpretative details allowing for key questions and points of research to be highlighted while enabling participants to guide the discussion to areas and experiences they deemed important, facilitating the collection of rich, nuanced data (Greenspan & Bolkosky, 2006: 433). This co-creation of knowledge, consistent with feminist qualitative approach, foregrounds participants' perception, situating their experiences within a broader analysis that considers cultural contexts and participant perspectives within broader sociological understandings of gender, knowledge production, and institutional power.

3. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Microaggressions

Microaggressions manifest as subtle, brief, indirect, and/or unconscious comments and behaviours that communicate prejudicial, hostile, or degrading beliefs about a group of often marginalized people, sustaining hierarchical ruling relations. They act and function in ways that are "pernicious", enabling individuals and systems to act with "subtle discrimination", covertly infusing into social, cultural, and professional environments (Basford et al., 2014: 341). This includes microinvalidations and microinsults which are "most often deliberate on the part of the microaggressor, whose intent is to hurt, oppress, or discriminate", convey with insensitivity, beliefs and opinions that are rude, and/or directly demeaning (Basford et al., 2014: 341). Microaggressions also exist in shaming rituals; they police patriarchal expectations by reinforcing social control and unequal power relations, discrediting, dismissing, denigrating, and stigmatizing the perspective and activities of the one being shamed.

Although gender research and advocacy centres have been established within Ghanaian universities to address the need to link informal and differential ways of navigating the "unwritten codes and conventions" related to gender disparity in the university and beyond (Britwum et al., 2014: 5). The formalization of these previously informal discourses on gender inequalities have altered university structures and introduced institutional frameworks that can be used by social actors to pursue gender equity (University of Ghana, 2022; Kiprop, 2025), including aims, objectives and policy-based practice such as gender sensitization. However, realizing ideals of gender equity, academic freedom and full and substantive participation of women academics within higher education requires specialized attention to the often informal ways in which women experience differential inclusion, such as the microaggressions reinforce gendered hierarchies and expressions of benevolent sexism can be used to frame and 'justify' gender inequality by reinforcing ideologies that reify women's 'natural' gender roles (Becker & Swim, 2011: 228; Vanderveer, (in press), undermining women's professional roles and professional advancement.

Operating within larger systems and institutions, microaggressions have "distributional effects: they reflect, reproduce, and magnify particular patterns of power" (Waylen, 2007; Hickey & Nazneen, 2019: 24). When paired with meritocratic ideologies and the removal of formal gender barriers, they mask differences in how women are treated in universities (Sue et al., 2008: 238). As such, microaggressions reinforce systems of power, not through open oppression but through intended or unintended actions that diminish position, agency, and influence (Basford et al., 2014: 341). For example, when a student calls his female professor "Auntie" or "Mummy" in a Ghanaian university, he does not necessarily question her right to teach, but undermines her authority and credibility reinforcing the belief that her defined role is that of caretaker while male colleagues are addressed as "Professor," "Dr." or "Sir," not "Daddy" or "Uncle"; a difference participants note is systemic and often goes unchallenged. These forms of differential treatment are ubiquitous, and it are often not noticed at all. It is important to note that the terms "Mummy" and "Aunty" are not terms of disrespect and are commonly used in Ghana. They serve as terms and salutations that show deference when first names are not appropriate. Although they denote respect, their familiarity combines with the gendered nature of the terms, and their associations with caretaking create attitudes and

behaviours that would not be considered appropriate with male faculty. These microaggressions and microinvalidations indicate internalized prejudices regarding female faculty, diminishing the social and professional status of women in comparison with their male counterparts; they reinforce gender norms and patriarchal hierarchies of power. These commonly used terms and identifiers first and foremost identify women faculty members by gender rather than by status, reinforcing gender roles and demarking professional roles and positions by gender rather than by achievement. They also act as part of broader systems of gendered expectations, which act to reinforce gender norms within broader patriarchal contexts.

During conversations with participants, I asked whether they had felt, noticed, experienced, or witnessed a difference in the treatment of men and women faculty in the classroom. While most indicated yes, several said no. Their answers reiterated ideas of equality, highlighted by comments that female faculty are respected and that women belong at the university and should be treated without distinction. However, discrepancies emerged when I probed further by asking questions about expectations for emotional labour, compassion, ease of marking, and differences in the deference shown to male and female faculty. We discussed gender norms ascribed to female faculty and engaged in role-reversal experiments in which male faculty assigned women's caretaking roles and responsibilities, raising questions about whether these patterns could be reversed and what the expectations behind them might look like. For those who initially noted no distinct differences in the expectations and treatment of male and female faculty, most began remarking on distinctions. While critically analyzing their observations and experiences, they expressed clear surprise at differences in behaviour and expectations as well as their prior lack of observation, demonstrating the internalization of gender roles, behaviours, and meritocratic mythology.

When I first spoke with "Mawusi", a PhD Candidate and Sessional Instructor in the Sciences, she was quietly adamant that there is no difference in the treatment between male and female faculty in the classroom, but when we discussed interactions within the classroom, she began to note distinctions: female faculty were expected to be obliging, care-taking and flexible, and male faculty were perceived as stern, professional and strict. When discussing how students interact with faculty, "Mawusi" noted the casual familiarity of referring to female faculty as "Mummy" or "Auntie" and female faculty were expected to approve requests for leniency while requests from male faculty were perceived as an exception rather than an expectation. This differential treatment reinforces the sexist, dichotomous framing of gender and from social and cultural traditions into the university and classroom, wherein gender roles produce expectations upon women to perform "counselling and welfare-type work with students and staff" (Manuh, 2007: 140), expectations not associated with male faculty. It is a process and divergence that demonstrates the accretion of gendered influence on social and cultural capital; a belief system and structure that is as pernicious as it is ubiquitous.

Microaggressions towards women faculty members act as part of a system of reinforcing and perpetuating the normalization of differences between men and women; this, in turn, perpetuates a normalized false belief in essentialist gender roles and responsibilities. The collective reinforcement of patriarchal structures seemingly 'justifies' the inequality experienced by women through its own reiteration (Basford et al., 2014: 243). Reinforcement increases the likelihood that the manifestations and impacts of microaggressions will be dismissed, underscoring the need to develop critical consciousness. Identifying microaggressions as discriminatory and unacceptable through a process of critical reflection, combined with dialogue, can encourage insight, empathy, and reshape behaviours and environments by halting inappropriate activity when it occurs.

Vanderveer (2024) notes that the internalization of benevolent sexism undermines women's roles, individually and collectively, increasing the likelihood that women will accept acts of discrimination while discounting or overlooking their consequences, including how this can undermine individual and collective resistance to gender discrimination (Vanderveer, 2024: 9-10). Gender discrimination thrives in social environments where ideologies of

meritocracy and gender neutrality promote policies and practices of equality rather than equity. This produces settings that situate gender discrimination as a historical artifact rather than an active social force, perpetuating a deficiency of awareness regarding the extent, prevalence, and impacts of sexism (Vanderveer, 2024: 10).

Challenging microaggressions

Some participants challenge the microaggressions they experience directly. Akosua refuses to accept this kind of discourse in her classroom. She described how students have mistaken her for a teaching assistant, referred to her as “Mummy” or “Auntie,” and expected her to act as an academic caretaker for them. These gendered microinvalidations represent and enact expectations that would be unthinkable to extend to a male faculty member. To challenge this, Akosua engages in a “pedagogy of discomfort” wherein students are invited to critically engage with their assumptions and “destabili[ze] their views of themselves and their worlds, reconstruct previously held views and, by doing so, to move to new insights and dispositions” (Bozalek, 2015: 94). In doing so, Akosua engages in critical sociological discourse and the cultural deconstruction of embedded gender roles and inferential sexism, challenging her students to critique the deeply internalized beliefs they are demonstrating and reinforcing.

Akosua's engagement in these informal conversations within the formal educational setting of the classroom has multiple impacts: (1) it transitions informal, inferential sexism from a social and cultural expression into a formal academic discussion, (2) transitions casual utterances into an opportunity for analytic critique, (3) discomforts gendered presumptions emphasizes (4) within a professional environment where she is the intellectual and professional expert and power holder. This process challenges gender norms and shifts gendered power dynamics. It is an academic, analytic experiential practice that engages with how all people are subject to and implicated in hegemonic discourses” (Bozalek, 2015: 94). Akosua's methods produce discursive environments where people are invited to engage in critical analysis, prompting them not only to better understand their sociocultural environment but also to discover who they are and who they refuse to be (Bozalek, 2015: 93).

Acts of microaggression are not limited to the student body. Akosua, whose upbringing focused on critical analysis and intellectual development was an environment where she “didn't grow up being censored” or “told what you can and cannot do because you are female”. Akosua noted how her minimal self-censorship has led to shaming and censure from male colleagues during a seminar that included a District Assembly official:

I've gotten in trouble in this department because a District Assembly official came to do a presentation.... [W]hen he presented, I actually sat there wanting to see if his colleagues could see the problem and fix it. So, they commented. Then he started getting defensive, which is the point at which I said “actually, your colleagues are right”. [The official] reported me to a colleague as having disrespected him. But for me, what was interesting about that encounter [was] ... that my colleague, [a] male colleague, actually thought he should call me on it.

While she and the official's colleague agreed that the official's argument was flawed, it was Akosua who was chastised by both the official and her male colleague for not showing sufficient deference and challenging an authority figure. Neither acknowledged how the official's male colleague was not chastised, the key difference between the two comments was the gender of the commentators, nor that Akosua was subjected to disproportionate treatment. This indicates a clear difference in expectation, treatment and power, expressed through disproportionate treatment, drawn along gender lines as well as “resistance to role modifications and support of a differential view of men and women” (Tougas et al., 1998: 1497) where shaming rituals are utilized to suppress opinion and/or dissent, police activities and reinforce dominant power structures.

Challenges to power are often shaped by relative access to power and resources, as individuals weigh the risks to their financial, familial, and employment security - factors that together reinforce ongoing systemic inequalities. People who are disempowered by the very systems they navigate - women, in particular - are often required to develop a nuanced understanding of those systems to evaluate and navigate the professional and reputational risks of speaking out and challenging power. As such, microaggressions find spaces to exist in sociocultural environments where overt hostility and punitive retribution are no longer tolerated. The rebuke that Akosua received is bureaucratic, gendered, and patriarchal, demonstrating the social and cultural bias embedded within university and political structures. She considers this example of gendered politics within the university a clear example of gender bias, as well as a learning opportunity regarding the benefits of practical self-censorship. Akosua notes that when she does engage in self-censorship, it is usually on the grounds of whether it will be productive or hurt an overall agenda of promoting gender equity: "[I]n spaces where sexism is at work [I make] a decision as to whether, in this particular context, what difference [confronting this bias] make or not". This negotiative feminist framework and methodology seeks to address social issues through constructive discourse and mutuality of respect (Nnaemeka, 2003: 377-378) while considering long-term goals and progressive gains. These 'lessons' in practical self-censorship can include norms that Akosua does not always recognize: "I'm not sure if I'm very good at that ... it's only when people respond [negatively] that I realize, oops, I was supposed to have not done this" (Akosua). However, when these experiences arise, they are instructive of ongoing inferential sexism, the barriers they produce, and the hierarchies they sustain. They also produce opportunities for engagement with critical, collaborative discourse and nego-feminist methodologies.

Akosua's pedagogical practices are demonstrations of micro-actions within a field of broader feminist practices. Her approach is radical: she pinpoints the roots of gender bias and chips away at the structures and beliefs that sustain them through practices of inclusive discourse. In doing so, she challenges beliefs, systems, and structures from the inside. Akosua's collaborative practices invite engagement; they are practices through which discussants can become involved, incentivized, and responsabilized to resist and refuse to sustain gender discrimination within and beyond the classroom. This process rejects a liability model of responsibility where marginalized groups are made responsible for challenging structural inequalities (Bozalek et al., 2015: 94) and, instead, advances a "social connection model of responsibility" wherein all participants hold social responsibility addressing systemic inequalities (Young (2011). This inclusive practice works within a nego-feminist theoretical and methodological framework of collaboration (Nnaemeka, 2003), which emphasizes inclusion, discourse, and action. It invites everyone to actively engage in recognizing and challenging systemic and ideological inequality. This practice can create "reflective solidarity" (Dean, 1996; Mohanty, 2003: 7) through group action and perspective, producing a collective "third voice (Mohanty, 2003: 7). It is a praxis that can facilitate the allyship essential to challenging gender-based discrimination (Kiprop, 2025: 14) and "condition future action in specific ways" (Young, 2001: 13) to produce micro, meso- and macro levels of social change across social, cultural and institutional environments.

Drawing upon "foundation[s] of shared values, attitudes, and institutions" (Etounga-Manguelle, 2000; Nnaemeka, 2003: 361), Akosua engages in a praxis that can have "determinate effects on the physical and cultural environment which condition future action in specific ways" (Young, 2001: 13), modeling agentic action and shared responsibility. Akosua not only engages with people in the present, but she also speaks to their futures. Drawing on her knowledge, positionality, and institutional power within a respected academic setting, she actively connects with students, peers, and government officials. Through collaborative and intentional practice, she opens possibilities for shaping future thinking, policies, and systems. This is a transformative praxis—one rooted in critical engagement and the reimagining of ideological and institutional futures.

Microaggressions reinforce defined gender roles and hierarchies by punishing non-conformity; conversely, punishing nonconformity reflexively implies that gender conformity can facilitate inclusion within patriarchal structures. But this is only effective if women self-police, constrain their ambitions and opinions so as not to threaten or make power holders uncomfortable; even then, women's position and status remain subject to overarching systems of power. As in all masculine organizations, "[h]omosociability", "fratriarchal loyalties," and "authoritarian and entrepreneurial masculinities" characterize the university environments concerned with efficiency, production, and prestige (Prichard, 1996; Alemán & Mart, 2014: 124) while "inequality regimes" enact "interrelated practices, processes, actions, and meanings" that maintain gender inequality (Acker, 2006; Alemán & Mart, 2014: 124). These systems present significant informal barriers to women academic, and when combined with gendered domestic and familial labour, these barriers constrain women's professional development and can be doubly impacted when met with resistance, ridicule or dismissal from peers and within the university (Manuh, 2007: 140) whose ideologies, ambitions or research interests challenge dominant ideologies and power holders; this inhibits the ability of women academics to receive the support necessary for achieving equal research, professional development and institutional success.

Bureaucratic approaches to 'equality' emphasize meritocratic logics and the removal of formal barriers (Tsikata, 2007: 36). This creates procedural space for box-ticking, facilitating tokenism rather than meaningful social, cultural, and systemic change. Ideologies of individualism and meritocracy present personal achievement as a personal attribute "rather than group membership" (Taylor & McKirnan, 1984; Tougas et al., 1998: 1488), muting and masking the acknowledgement and critique of systemic disadvantages. These processes reinforce, normalize, and 'justify' exclusionary stereotypes and discourses in which women are represented as much as can be, or seek to be, within professional academic spaces. This can result in a tokenistic 'proof' of opportunity - a tool that can be weaponized to argue that systemic change is not necessary, thereby sustaining systemic inequalities under false perceptions of equality. To challenge this, it is crucial to view women's representation as part of a critical, overarching process of inclusion, rendering it essential rather than instrumental (Nazneen & Hickey, 2019: 8).

4. CONCLUSION

Microaggressions act as informal barriers that represent and reinforce differences of treatment, shaping differences of experience and facilitating differential inclusion; overt and covert, conscious and subconscious biases based upon gender, perpetuating gender inequality. Microaggressions and informal barriers impact women's experiences, diminishing perceptions and enactments of women's power, authority, capacity, and place, reinforcing patriarchal power dynamics. Participants in this study are critically engaging with these challenges and actively working to challenge biases, discriminatory actions, and professional barriers through critical dialogue. Their intellectual, social and emotional labour humanizes impacts and makes gender hegemonies and their impacts tangible. By encouraging actors to engage in identifying and confronting overt and covert biases, they make actors responsible for their (in)actions and their impacts on others, (re)shaping social environments towards more equitable practices. However, informal and ideological barriers continue to significantly hinder women's professional development and achievement. Sexist beliefs and ideologies permeate social environments and institutional systems, reinforcing informal barriers that act as a means of maintaining the status quo.

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